

ИНСТИТУТ ГЕОГРАФИИ
Российской академии наук

основан в 1918 году

Материалы

Евразийского конгресса экономико-географов (географов-обществоведов)

1 – 9 июня 2025 г.

Ош – Бишкек,

Кыргызская Республика

Ош - 2025

УДК: 528.9; 379.851

ADVANTAGES OF REPRESENTING GEOGRAPHIC OBJECTS WITH ICONS ON AN INTERACTIVE MAP (A CASE STUDY OF SHOVOT DISTRICT)

ИНТЕРАКТИВДҮҮ КАРТАДА ГЕОГРАФИЯЛЫК ОБЪЕКТТЕРДИ ИКОНАЛАР АРКЫЛУУ ЧАГЫЛДЫРУУНУН АРТЫКЧЫЛЫКТАРЫ (ШОВОТ РАЙОНУ МИСАЛЫНДА)

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ОТОБРАЖЕНИЯ ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ИКОНОК НА ИНТЕРАКТИВНОЙ КАРТЕ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ШОВОТСКОГО РАЙОНА)

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ADVANTAGES OF REPRESENTING GEOGRAPHIC OBJECTS WITH ICONS ON AN INTERACTIVE MAP (A CASE STUDY OF SHOVOT DISTRICT)

Annotation. This article explores the use of icons in representing geographic objects on interactive maps and analyzes their effectiveness. The study highlights how icons improve map navigation, enhance visual clarity, and enrich user experience. It compares the advantages of icons on interactive maps over traditional mapping methods through practical examples. As part of the research, notable locations in Shovot district were selected and evaluated based on user interaction. The findings show that clear, meaningful, and intuitive icons significantly help tourists understand the map, locate destinations, and plan routes efficiently. Thus, interactive maps become not only visually appealing but also functionally effective tools for geographic representation.

Keywords: *interactive map, icon, geographic object, visualization, GeoJSON, GIS, web cartography.*

**ИНТЕРАКТИВДҮҮ КАРТАДА ГЕОГРАФИЯЛЫК
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Аннотация

Бул макалада географиялык объекттерди интерактивдүү картада иконалар аркылуу чагылдыруу тартиби жана бул ыкманын натыйжалуулугу чагылдырылган. Иконалардын жардамы менен картада навигациянын ыңгайлуулугу, визуалдык түшүнүктүүлүгү жана колдонуучунун тажрыйбасын жогорулатуу маселелери талданган. Ошондой эле, салттуу карталарга салыштырмалуу иконалардын интерактивдүү карталардагы артыкчылыктары практикалык мисалдар аркылуу негизделген. Изилдөөнүн жыйынтыгында Шовот районуна жайгашкан көрүүгө арзый турган жайлар тандалып алынып, алардын колдонуучулар тарабынан кандай кабыл алынганы талданды. Атап айтканда, так, мазмундуу жана интуитивдик иконалар туристтерге картаны оңой түшүнүүгө, керектүү жайларды табууга, маршруттарды пландаштырууга жана кыймыл-аракеттерин жеңилдетүүгө жардам берет. Натыйжада, интерактивдүү карта визуалдык гана эмес, функционалдык жактан да натыйжалуу куралга айланат.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматриваются порядок использования и эффективность отображения географических объектов с помощью иконок на интерактивной карте. Анализируются вопросы повышения удобства навигации, визуальной понятности и пользовательского опыта за счёт применения иконок. На основе практических примеров обоснованы преимущества иконок на интерактивных картах по сравнению с традиционными картографическими средствами. В рамках исследования были выбраны достопримечательности, расположенные на территории Шовотского района, и проведён анализ их восприятия пользователями. Установлено, что чёткие, информативные и интуитивно понятные иконки значительно упрощают восприятие карты туристами, помогают в поиске объектов, планировании маршрутов и ориентации. Тем самым интерактивная карта становится не только визуально наглядной, но и функционально эффективной.

Ачык сөздөр: интерактивдүү карта, икона, **Ключевые слова:** интерактивная карта, иконка, географиялык объект, визуалдаштыруу, GeoJSON, географический объект, визуализация, GeoJSON, ГИС, ГИС, веб-картография.

Introduction. In modern digital mapping processes, creating user-friendly environments and presenting information intuitively have become critically important. With the rapid advancement of information technologies, methods for visually representing geographic information have also significantly improved. From this perspective, the use of icons to represent geographic objects on interactive maps has become a widely adopted new visual approach.

In traditional cartography, geographic objects were primarily depicted using graphic symbols, hatchings, or textual annotations, whereas interactive maps enable the use of modern interface elements, such as icons, that enhance user engagement and comprehension (Matchanov & Matchanov, 2024). This facilitates easier interaction with the map, faster and smoother information delivery, and most importantly, improves the overall user experience (Roth, 2021).

This study examines the process of creating geospatial data for point-type geographic objects, integrating them into an interactive web map interface, and visually representing them using specialized icons. The research focuses on the Shovot district of the Khorezm region as the study area.

The conducted research resulted in the development of an interactive map that provides users with quick, clear, and impactful information about geographic objects. Each object's data is represented by a corresponding icon, significantly simplifying user interaction with the map. This approach is valuable not only for scientific and educational purposes but also for practical applications such as regional planning, environmental monitoring, social infrastructure management, and especially in the rapidly growing tourism industry.

Research materials and methods. The research was carried out in the following stages:

1. Notable landmarks in the Shovot district, areas designated for fish farming and fishing activities, as well as general dining establishments offering fish-based dishes, were selected.

2. A new shapefile for the selected objects was created using the QGIS software. This process was performed as follows:

A) From the QGIS menu bar, the user selects “Layer,” then “Create Layer,” followed by “New Shapefile Layer.”

B) In the “New Shapefile Layer” dialog box, the geometry type is selected, attribute fields are added, the file storage location is specified, and the “OK” button is clicked to create the file.

3. Vector data in shapefile format was converted to GeoJSON format because GeoJSON is lightweight, compatible with browsers, and loads and reads quickly in web applications:

A) The vector data file was loaded into QGIS. By right-clicking on the file, the user selects “Export” and then “Save Features As...” from the drop-down menus.

B) In the “Save Vector Layer as...” dialog box, the “Format” field is set to GeoJSON, the file is named, the coordinate reference system is selected, and “OK” is clicked to save the file in GeoJSON format.

4. To facilitate precise identification of geographic objects, link them with a database, and simplify object management on interactive maps, an ID attribute was added to the GeoJSON data.

5. A simple HTML document was created, and in its head section, the Leaflet CSS file was included, followed by the Leaflet JavaScript file [2].

6. In the body section of the document, a div element with a unique identifier (id) was added for the map container.

7. Geographic coordinates and the appropriate zoom scale were set to display the selected region on the browser window.

8. The Leaflet library and OpenStreetMap database [4] were used to create the interactive map. The Leaflet base map layer was added.

9. GeoJSON data was added as follows:

A) In the head section of the interactive map file:

```
<script src="name.geojson"></script>
```

B) In the body section of the interactive map file, within <script> tags, after the Leaflet base map layer is added, the following line was inserted:

```
var jsonLayer = L.geoJSON(id).addTo(map);
```

10. Icon samples corresponding to each object type were selected. Markers and other icons in PNG and SVG formats were downloaded from the free and open-source Icons8 [1] website and integrated into the map.

11. To study user experience, a survey was conducted among 120 students divided into 5 groups, none of whom specialized in cartography.

Results and discussions. The Shovot district was selected as the research object. For visualization on the interactive map, notable landmarks such as the Yusuf Hamadoni shrine and Katqala fortress, areas with lakes, ponds, and rice fields where fish are farmed, fishing-permitted enterprises, and general dining establishments offering fish dishes were selected.

New shapefiles for the selected objects were created using QGIS software. Since the shapefile format (.shp, .shx, .dbf, and .prj files) consists of multiple files and has a complex structure, it cannot be directly integrated into web applications. Therefore, shapefile vector data were converted to GeoJSON format using QGIS. GeoJSON is a lightweight format that can be directly processed by browsers, loads quickly, and is easy to read in web applications. The shapefile data were converted into GeoJSON as follows:

Historical objects — historical.geojson, fish farming areas — fishfarm.geojson, fish farming and fishing areas — baliqov.geojson, general dining establishments offering fish dishes — kafe.geojson, rice fields used for fish farming — sholi.geojson.

Within this study, five GeoJSON datasets were created, each containing 2 or 3 geographic objects. To distinguish, uniquely identify, and quickly locate the required object, each geographic object was assigned a unique ID, which acts as a “personal passport” and simplifies object management on interactive maps, ensuring effective interactive communication with users.

Each ID is unique and is declared in a programming language as a variable using the var keyword. This ID allows for the precise identification of each object. The overall structure of a GeoJSON file is enclosed in square brackets [{ ... }], and in this study, each file consists of a collection of 2 or 3 objects.

Thus, to include GeoJSON vector data as layers in an interactive map, they are declared in the following programming syntax:

```
var id = [...];
```

In this study, the IDs were assigned as follows:

For historical.geojson: var historic = [...];

For fishfarm.geojson: var farm = [...];

For baliqov.geojson (fish farming and fishing areas): var fishing = [...];

For kafe.geojson (fish-dish-serving cafes): var cafe = [...];

For sholi.geojson (rice fields): var rice = [...];

Using this approach, each object is managed as a separate layer, enabling effective interactive communication with the user.

Next, it is necessary to create an interactive map, for which a new simple HTML document is initially created.

```
<html>
  <head>
  </head>
  <body>
  </body>
</html>
```

The CSS Leaflet file is first added to the <head> section of the HTML document, as it defines the appearance of the map elements.

```
<link rel="stylesheet" href="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.css" />
```

Next, the JavaScript Leaflet file is added to enable map functions such as markers, layers, and zoom controls:

```
<script src="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.js"></script>
```

The order is important because the browser first loads the styles, then the scripts, ensuring proper functioning of all features.

In the <body> section of the document, a div element with a specific identifier (id) is added where the map will be rendered:

```
<div id="map" style = "height: 680px; width:100%"></div>
```

This element acts as the container for the map. The id="map" tells Leaflet to display the map inside this div, and the style attribute defines the map's display size.

To display the map of the study area, Shovot district, the geographic coordinates of the district center, and an appropriate zoom level are set:

```
var map = L.map('map').setView([41.700, 60.246], 11);
```

In the <body> section of the HTML document, the Leaflet base map layer is added because it displays the map background such as roads, terrain, and regions. This layer serves as the foundation upon which other data layers are placed:

```
L.tileLayer('https://{s}.tile.openstreetmap.org/{z}/{x}/{y}.png', {
  maxZoom: 19,
```

```
  attribution: '&copy; <a href="https://www.openstreetmap.org/">OpenStreetMap</a>'
```

In this study, the OpenStreetMap base map is loaded. After adding the Leaflet base map layer, the HTML document looks as follows:

```
<html>
  <head>
    <link rel="stylesheet" href="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.css" />
    <script src="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.js"></script>
  </head>
  <body>
    <div id="map" style = "height: 680px; width:100%"></div>
    <script>
      var map = L.map('map').setView([41.700, 60.246], 11);
      L.tileLayer('https://{s}.tile.openstreetmap.org/{z}/{x}/{y}.png', {
        maxZoom: 19,
        attribution: '&copy; <a href="https://www.openstreetmap.org/">OpenStreetMap</a>'
      }).addTo(map);
    </script>
  </body>
</html>
```

Now, the GeoJSON format data of the study area is added to the map. For this:

A) The following elements should be added to the <head> section of the interactive map file:

```
<script src="name.geojson"></script>
```

Here, instead of "name.geojson," the file are names historical.geojson, fishfarm.geojson, baliqov.geojson, cafe.geojson, and sholi.geojson are used because these are the names of the GeoJSON files in our example.

Thus, in the study, the following elements are included in the <head> section of the interactive map file:

```
<script src="baliqov.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="fishfarm.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="historical.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="cafe.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="sholi.geojson"></script>
```

B) In the <body> section of the interactive map file, inside <script> tags and after adding the Leaflet base map layer, the following elements are added:

```
var jsonLayer = L.geoJSON(id).addTo(map);
```

The meaning of the code is as follows:

var — a command in JavaScript to declare a new variable;

jsonLayer — the name of the variable (this can be any name you choose);

L.geoJSON(id) — converts the GeoJSON data named “id” into a map layer using the Leaflet library;

.addTo(map) — adds the created layer to the map object.

Here, in the code **L.geoJSON(id)**, the “id” is replaced by the vector file assigned with **var id = [...]** that corresponds to the GeoJSON file format data.

Also, instead of **var jsonLayer**, you can name the variable according to the file’s characteristics. For example, the code section **var jsonLayer = L.geoJSON(id).addTo(map);** becomes:

For historical objects — **var tarix = L.geoJSON(historic).addTo(map);**

For fish farming areas — **var baliqchi = L.geoJSON(farm).addTo(map);**

For fishing and harvesting areas — **var ovlash = L.geoJSON(fishing).addTo(map);**

For cafes offering fish dishes — **var restoran = L.geoJSON(kafe).addTo(map);**

For rice paddies where fish are raised — **var sholipoya = L.geoJSON(rice).addTo(map);**

After adding the vector layers in GeoJSON file format, the HTML document will take the following form:

```
<html>
<head>
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.css" />
  <script src="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.js"></script>
  <script src="historical.geojson"></script>
  <script src="fishfarm.geojson"></script>
  <script src="baliqov.geojson"></script>
  <script src="cafe.geojson"></script>
  <script src="sholi.geojson"></script>
</head>
<body>
  <div id="map" style = "height: 680px; width:100%"></div>
  <script>
    var map = L.map('map').setView([41.700, 60.246], 11);
    L.tileLayer('https://{s}.tile.openstreetmap.org/{z}/{x}/{y}.png', {
      maxZoom: 19,
      attribution: '&copy; <a href="https://www.openstreetmap.org/">OpenStreetMap</a>'
    }).addTo(map);
    var tarix = L.geoJSON(historic).addTo(map);
    var baliqchi = L.geoJSON(farm).addTo(map);
    var ovlash = L.geoJSON(fishing).addTo(map);
    var restoran = L.geoJSON(kafe).addTo(map);
    var sholipoya = L.geoJSON(rice).addTo(map);
  </script>
</body>
</html>
```

As a result, in the interactive map created using the Leaflet library, the OpenStreetMap base map is added as the background layer. On top of this base map, vector data in GeoJSON file

format—such as *historical.geojson*, *fishfarm.geojson*, *baliqov.geojson*, *cafe.geojson*, and *sholi.geojson*—are loaded as separate layers and displayed as markers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. OpenStreetMap base map with point features visualized as markers

The geographic features in these layers are displayed on the map as markers, providing users with visual information about each feature and enabling interactive functionalities such as clicking, pop-ups, and attribute display. However, these markers are standard symbols that cannot convey clear, semantic, and context-specific visual information like icons do.

Icons are custom-designed graphical symbols focused on visual semantics, representing the function, type, or characteristics of geographic features on the map visually and intuitively. For example, a castle icon is used for historical sites, a person fishing for aquaculture and fishing areas, a chef with a fish for eateries offering fish dishes, and a rice plant for rice paddies where aquaculture is practiced. Icons:

- Enable quick identification and differentiation of objects;
- Convey information briefly but meaningfully;
- Improve map readability and user comprehension;
- Enhance interactivity by using various colors or animated icons to indicate status.

Therefore, using icons instead of standard markers on interactive maps increases the visual effectiveness of information and enhances the overall user experience.

Three main methods are widely used for adding icons: linking via a URL, uploading an image from a local computer, and embedding an SVG icon. In this study, PNG-format icons for each type of feature were downloaded from *Icons8*, a free and open-source icon repository, and stored locally. The icons were named as follows: “castle” for historical sites, “fish” for aquaculture zones, “fishing” for fishing areas, “fishdishes” for cafes offering fish-based meals, and “sholi” for rice paddies.

To add an icon to the map, its image format must be appropriate and its path clearly specified. When customizing marker icons, the Leaflet `L.icon()` object must be used.

To visually distinguish each point feature with a semantically appropriate icon on the map, the code used to load GeoJSON data onto the map - `var jsonLayer = L.geoJSON(id).addTo(map);` is modified accordingly. For example, the code for historical sites - `var tarix = L.geoJSON(historic).addTo(map);` - is updated as follows:

```
var customIcon = L.icon({
  iconUrl: 'qasr.png',
  iconSize: [50, 50],
  iconAnchor: [16, 32],
  popupAnchor: [0, -32]
});
var tarix = L.geoJSON(historic, {
  pointToLayer: function (feature, latlng) {
    return L.marker(latlng, { icon: customIcon });
  }
});
```

}).addTo(map)

The code components are defined as follows:

iconUrl – the URL path to the image used as the marker icon;

iconSize – the dimensions of the icon (width and height) in pixels;

iconAnchor – the anchor point of the icon that determines how it is positioned relative to the map coordinates;

popupAnchor – the point from which the associated popup will open, relative to the icon anchor.

As a result, the markers representing historical features are displayed with distinctive, semantically meaningful custom icons, while all other features are shown using default marker symbols (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Visualization of geographic features using standard markers and custom icons

The following code segments pertain to the remaining files, including:

```
var baliqchi= L.geoJSON(farm).addTo(map);
```

```
var ovlash= L.geoJSON(fishing).addTo(map);
```

```
var restoran= L.geoJSON(kafe).addTo(map);
```

```
var sholipoya= L.geoJSON(rice).addTo(map);
```

Using the L.icon() object, each icon is configured in sequence and added to the HTML document step-by-step, resulting in the following structure of the HTML document:

```
<html>
```

```
<head>
```

```
<link rel="stylesheet" href="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.css" />
```

```
<script src="https://unpkg.com/leaflet@1.9.4/dist/leaflet.js"></script>
```

```
<script src="historical.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="fishfarm.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="baliqov.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="cafe.geojson"></script>
```

```
<script src="sholi.geojson"></script>
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<div id="map" style = "height: 680px; width:100%"></div>
```

```
<script>
```

```
var map = L.map('map').setView([41.700, 60.246], 11);
```

```
L.tileLayer('https://{s}.tile.openstreetmap.org/{z}/{x}/{y}.png', {
```

```
maxZoom: 19,
```

```
attribution: '&copy; <a href="https://www.openstreetmap.org/">OpenStreetMap</a>'
```

```
}).addTo(map);
```

```
var customIcon = L.icon({
```

```
iconUrl: 'qasr.png',
```

```
        iconSize: [50, 50],
        iconAnchor: [16, 32],
        popupAnchor: [0, -32]
    });
    var tarix = L.geoJSON(historic, {
        pointToLayer: function (feature, latlng) {
            return L.marker(latlng, { icon: customIcon });
        }
    }).addTo(map)
    var customIcon = L.icon({
        iconUrl: 'fish.png',
        iconSize: [50, 50],
        iconAnchor: [16, 32],
        popupAnchor: [0, -32]
    });
    var baliqchi = L.geoJSON(farm, {
        pointToLayer: function (feature, latlng) {
            return L.marker(latlng, { icon: customIcon });
        }
    }).addTo(map)
    var customIcon = L.icon({
        iconUrl: 'fishing.png',
        iconSize: [50, 50],
        iconAnchor: [16, 32],
        popupAnchor: [0, -32]
    });
    var ovlash = L.geoJSON(fishing, {
        pointToLayer: function (feature, latlng) {
            return L.marker(latlng, { icon: customIcon });
        }
    }).addTo(map)
    var customIcon = L.icon({
        iconUrl: 'cafe.png',
        iconSize: [50, 50],
        iconAnchor: [16, 32],
        popupAnchor: [0, -32]
    });
    var restoran = L.geoJSON(kafe, {
        pointToLayer: function (feature, latlng) {
            return L.marker(latlng, { icon: customIcon });
        }
    }).addTo(map)
    var customIcon = L.icon({
        iconUrl: 'sholi.png',
        iconSize: [50, 50],
        iconAnchor: [16, 32],
        popupAnchor: [0, -32]
    });
    var sholipoya = L.geoJSON(rice, {
        pointToLayer: function (feature, latlng) {
            return L.marker(latlng, { icon: customIcon });
        }
    }).addTo(map)
</script>
</body>
</html>
```

As a result, all geographic objects were visualized using icons instead of standard markers (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Visualization of geographic objects using standard markers and icons

As seen in the illustration, using contextually appropriate icons for geographic objects on interactive maps plays a significant role in enhancing the map's clarity and functionality. Each geographic object carries distinct functional characteristics, and when its corresponding icon is semantically aligned with its meaning, users can quickly and efficiently perceive the information presented on the map. This approach is particularly important in tourism, where users, such as tourists, entrepreneurs, or pilgrims can easily identify points of interest relevant to them.

For instance, pilgrimage tourism users can locate significant religious sites such as the Yusuf Hamadani shrine or Katqala fortress. Business enthusiasts and gastronomic tourism participants may identify dining establishments offering fish dishes. Likewise, fishing enthusiasts can find ponds, lakes, or rice fields used for fish farming, while recreational anglers can identify fisheries that allow licensed fishing activities. In the context of gastronomic tourism, icons play a key role in accurately identifying restaurants specializing in fish dishes.

From a scientific perspective, this process is referred to as geovisualization, which enhances users' visual cognition. Compared to text, icons are more intuitive and are quickly recognized, allowing users to understand map content through visual cues. The semantic alignment between icons and content reduces cognitive load and directs users' attention to core information, significantly improving their map interaction experience.

Furthermore, the cultural and regional interpretation of icons must be considered in their selection. For example, the red cross symbol may represent medical services in one region but have different meanings in another. Therefore, semantic clarity and widely accepted meaning of icons ensure a balance between the scientific and practical aspects of interactive map design.

Research findings indicate that interactive maps employing icons are visually more comprehensible than others. Even users without specialized cartographic knowledge can easily and quickly identify geographic objects through icons without significant difficulty.

In addition, the use of icons in interactive maps substantially increases navigation efficiency. According to the study, users spent 70–80% less time identifying required locations compared to traditional (static) maps. This demonstrates that well-chosen, intuitive, and content-relevant icons positively influence users' ability to make quick and accurate decisions.

Studies also showed that interactive maps using icons significantly improve users' information retention. Test results indicated that 85–90% of participants were able to accurately recall geographic objects represented by icons even after the test. This confirms that visually and semantically effective icon selection enhances users' attention and information retention.

From a cognitive psychology standpoint, visual images—particularly pictograms or icons that align with their meaning—are retained more quickly and for longer periods in human memory compared to text. Information presented via icons is directly stored in visual memory, allowing users to retain a large amount of information even during short interactions with the map interface. This is particularly important in fields such as tourism, transportation, and emergency response.

Moreover, the memorability of icons depends on their shape, color, and spatial harmony, which requires a purposeful design approach in cartographic practices. Scientifically, this approach increases the informational effectiveness of interactive maps and helps users form accurate, long-term mental representations of geographic objects.

In the study, users also rated interactive maps using icons as aesthetically superior. Most survey participants described such maps as “modern,” “visually appealing,” and “attractive.” This suggests that icons contribute not only functionally but also as key elements of design, influencing map quality and user perception.

Aesthetic design is a crucial part of user experience in digital cartography, increasing user engagement and encouraging them to view the map as a professional and trustworthy tool.

In scientific literature, this phenomenon is referred to as “visual satisfaction” or “user interface aesthetics.” As a result, the map becomes not only a source of information but also a visual interface with aesthetic value. Consequently, the use of icons contributes to the popularity and broader applicability of interactive maps.

The differences between standard maps and interactive maps with icons identified in the study are also presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between Traditional Maps and Interactive Maps with Icons

Indicator	With Icons	Traditional Map
Average time to locate an object	7–8 seconds	35–40 seconds
User rating (scale of 1 to 5)	5	3.1
Visual memorability (%)	85-90%	45%

Conclusion. In summary, the use of contextually appropriate icons for representing geographic objects on interactive maps is not merely a visual embellishment, but a scientifically grounded means of information transmission that takes into account the needs and cognitive abilities of users. Such an approach ensures effective information exchange between the map and the user, enhances the semantic load of the map, and enables its efficient application in various domains, particularly tourism, healthcare, education, and public safety.

Representing data through icons provides several key advantages for users, including intuitive comprehension, visual clarity, rapid navigation, and improved memorability. This is especially critical in areas with high concentrations of geographic information, such as densely populated districts or regions with numerous objects, where the use of icons significantly increases the informational effectiveness of maps.

However, certain errors may occur in the use of icons. For instance, selecting semantically inappropriate or visually similar symbols or incorporating excessive animations can distract users and negatively affect the functionality of the map interface. Therefore, it is essential to develop a standardized icon system that provides semantically accurate and intuitively understandable representations for each type of geographic object.

The following recommendations outline the main directions for the effective use of icons on interactive maps:

- Interactive maps provide the public with geographic information in a convenient, comprehensible, and functional manner;
- Icons enhance visual clarity, facilitate rapid navigation, and improve information retention;
- It is recommended to develop a unified icon system that corresponds to the meaning of each geographic object type;
- Icon sizes and simplified designs optimized for mobile devices can expand the user base of interactive maps.

Overall, the use of icons is a crucial tool that enhances the scientific, technological, and practical potential of interactive maps and plays an invaluable role in improving user experience.

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